

**Ukrainian Conference
with International Participation**

**CHEMISTRY, PHYSICS
AND
TECHNOLOGY OF SURFACE**

**11-12 October 2023
Kyiv
Ukraine**

Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry
of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Scientific Council

“Chemistry and Technology of Surface Modification”
Interbranch Scientific and Technical Complex “Surface Chemistry”

Ukrainian Conference with International Participation
**“CHEMISTRY, PHYSICS AND
TECHNOLOGY OF SURFACE”**

Book of abstracts

11–12 October, 2023
Kyiv
Ukraine

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Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Scientific Council “Chemistry and Technology of Surface Modification”
Interbranch Scientific and Technical Complex “Surface Chemistry”

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Conference Program

October 11, Wednesday

9:00 – 9:45 Registration of participants

10:00 – 10:25 Opening of the Conference at the Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Academician of NAS of Ukraine, Professor M. Kartel

Oral Session 1

Chair: Professor M. Kartel

10:25 – 10:50 V.M. Gun'ko, V.V. Turov. Colligative properties of various liquid blends vs. temperature under confined space effects in pores of different adsorbents (*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).

10:50 – 11:05 Group Photo

11:05 – 11:30 Coffee break

Oral Session 2

Chair: Professor V. Gun'ko

11:30 – 11:55 O.N. Kalugin^{1,2}, M.M. Blazhynska^{1,2,3}, D.S. Stepaniuk^{1,2}, V.A. Koverga^{1,2,4}, A.V. Kyrychenko¹, V.V. Ivanov¹, F.-A. Miannay², A. Idrissi². **D205 dye at the TiO₂ / ionic and molecular liquids interface: a molecular modelling study** (*¹Department of Inorganic Chemistry, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Ukraine, ²University of Lille, CNRS UMR 8516 LASIRE - Laboratoire Avancé de Spectroscopie pour les Interactions la Réactivité et l'environnement, France, ³Université de Lorraine, LPCT-UMR 7019 CNRS, Laboratoire de Physique et Chimie Théoriques, Vandœuvre-lès-Nancy, France, ⁴Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Illinois at Chicago, United States, Materials Science Division, Argonne National Laboratory, Lemont, Illinois, United States*).

11:55 – 12:20 L.A. Karachevtseva¹, M.T. Kartel², S.I. Pokutnii². **Giant optical absorption of a multilayer nanosystem of semiconductors and dielectrics** (*¹V.E. Lashkaryov Institute of Semiconductor Physics, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ²Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).

12:20 – 12:40 O.E. Baibara¹, M.V. Radchenko¹, M.E. Bugaiova¹, A.I. Ievtushenko¹, Y.A. Stelmakh², L.A. Krushinskaya². **The effect of magnetic field on thermoelectric properties of ferromagnetic nanocomposites Co/TiO₂** (*¹Frantsevych Institute for Problems of Material Science, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ²E.O. Paton Electric Welding Institute, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).

83. **L.V. Nosach**¹, E.M. Pakhlov¹, E. Skwarek². **Mechanosorption modifying of nanosilica with chitosan in a gaseous dispersion medium** (¹*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Maria Curie-Skłodowska University, Lublin, Poland*).
84. **Y.A. Onanko**¹, D.V. Charnyi¹, M.V. Yatsiuk¹, E.M. Matselyuk¹, A.P. Onanko², O.P. Dmytrenko², M.P. Kulish², T.M. Pinchuk-Rugal², V.M. Popruzhko², L.I. Kurochka², P.P. Ilyin². **Mechanical spectroscopy of SiO₂, radiation functionalized nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polyamide, polyvinylchloride, polyethylene** (¹*Institute of Water Problems and Land Reclamation, NAAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Faculty of Physics, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine*).
85. **Y.A. Onanko**¹, D.V. Charnyi¹, M.V. Yatsiuk¹, E.M. Matselyuk¹, A.P. Onanko², O.P. Dmytrenko², M.P. Kulish², T.M. Pinchuk-Rugal², V.M. Popruzhko², A.M. Gaponov², L.I. Kurochka², P.P. Ilyin². **Synergy of anelastic and elastic deformations in SiO₂, radiation functionalized nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polyamide, polyethylene, polyvinylchloride** (¹*Institute of Water Problems and Land Reclamation, NAAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Faculty of Physics, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine*).
86. **O.I. Oranska**, Yu.I. Gornikov. **Solid-phase reactions in the composites fumed silica - calcium acetate** (*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
87. **N.I. Pavlyshche**¹, A.V. Korotun^{1,2}, V.P. Kurbatsky¹. **Absorption properties of nanocomposites with randomly arranged spheroidal metal inclusions** (¹*National University Zaporizhzhia Politechnic, Ukraine*, ²*G.V. Kurdyumov Institute for Metal Physics, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
88. **V.V. Petryshyn**^{1,2}, N.V. Stoliarchuk², V.V. Tomina², **I.V. Melnyk**^{2,3}. **Trimethylaminopropyl-functionalized silica hybrids for the removal of heavy metal anions from water** (¹*National University of Kyiv-Mohyla Academy, Ukraine*, ²*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ³*Institute of Geotechnics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Kosice*).
89. **N.M. Permyakova**¹, T.B. Zheltonozhskaya¹, V.V. Klepko¹, N.V. Kozak¹, D.O. Klymchuk². **Preparation of xanthan-based nanomaterials with incorporated cobalt nanoparticles** (¹*Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Laboratory of Electron Microscopy, M.G. Kholodny Institute of Botany, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
90. **I.S. Petrik**¹, V.A. Moldavska^{1,2}, N.P. Smirnova¹, A.P. Naumenko², O.I. Oranska¹, M.V. Borysenko¹. **Photocatalytical and anticorrosial properties of nanostructured coatings based on tungsten doped titania** (¹*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine*).
91. A.M. Eremenko¹, **I.S. Petrik**¹, A.P. Naumenko². **Concentration-dependent fluorescence of quercetin in aqueous solutions of ions and colloids of silver nanoparticles** (¹*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine*).
92. **S.I. Pokutnii**¹, N.G. Shkoda¹, A.D. Terets^{1,2}. **Nanophotonics of perovskite nanocrystals: Theory** (¹*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Faculty of Physics, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine*).
93. **S.L. Prokopenko**¹, R.V. Mazurenko^{1,2}, A. Hercog², G.M. Gunja¹, S.M. Makhno^{1,3}, P.P. Gorbyk¹. **Electrophysical properties of polymer nanocomposites based on carbon nanotubes modified with cobalt ferrite** (¹*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Centre of Polymer and Carbon Materials, Polish Academy of Sciences, Zabrze*, ³*Ningbo University of Technology, P.R. China*).

Mechanical spectroscopy of SiO₂, radiation functionalized nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polyamide, polyvinylchloride, polyethylene

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In this work mechanical characteristics of nanocomposites based on polymers with multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MCNT) was researched [1].

Illustration of the window for processing data of quasitransversal elastic waves velocity $V_{\perp} = 960 \pm 10$ m/sec measuring in nanocomposite polyamide (NH(CH₂)₅CO)_n + 0,2% MCNT is represented in Figure. The increase of nanocomposite crystalline degree at growth of multiwalled carbon nanotubes concentration, filling with the nanotubes of matrix results in the decline of content of well-organized phase.

Fig. Illustration of the window for processing data of quasitransversal elastic waves velocity $V_{\perp} = 960$ m/sec measuring in nanocomposite polyamide + 0,2% MCNT by pulse phase ultrasonic method at frequency $f_{\perp} \approx 0,7$ MHz.

$$\text{Logarithmic decrement of attenuation } \delta = \ln \left(\frac{A_{n+1}}{A_n} \right) = \ln \left(\frac{120}{118} \right) \approx (1.68 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-2}$$

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1. A.P. Onanko, V.V. Kuryliuk, Y.A. Onanko, *et al.* J. Nano- Electron. Phys. **14**(6) (2022) 06029(7).